

METHODS OF USING TECHNOLOGIES THAT DEVELOP STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**Nazarova Nilufar Juraevna**

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Annotation: The article is aimed at educating the thinking ability of students and young people, in which the task of education in the current world conditions is to educate young people who can think and have critical thinking skills, the importance of using interactive methods in critical thinking, personal value. An analysis of the stages of the teaching process for the development, self-awareness and realization of the child and its development is given.

Key words: self-awareness, thinking style, critical thinking ability, creative thinking, cognitive activity, communication skills, pedagogical technology.

In Uzbekistan, we are getting more and more opportunities to control our own destiny and improve our lives, which the previous generations dreamed of. Self-awareness, self-study and education of the way of thinking [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] play an important role.

Currently, attention is being paid more and more to education of thinking ability of pupils and students. In 1992, at the International Council on Education in Mexico City, in today's rapidly changing world, the task of universities should be to prepare students who can think and have critical thinking skills. It was within the scope of reading, writing, memorizing, remembering, analyzing evidence, and solving tasks, which are the traditional requirements of higher educational institutions. However, the necessary rules about how to do it, especially thinking and thinking creatively, were not instilled or changed. Therefore, their ability to draw logical conclusions and the level of abstract thinking could not rise to the level of the spirit of the time.

John Dewey (American philosopher and pedagogue): stated that the main task of the current education system is to "teach a person to think". Combining teaching and learning with creative thinking is an important task of modern education. Without raising the thinking process and its mechanism to the modern technological level, the problems of why this is not happening, this is happening or why this is not happening, this is happening remain unanswered. Today, in

the social and economic development of our society, the issue of educating independent, free and critical-thinking young people is the most urgent task for Uzbekistan. Therefore, in organizing the educational process of academic lyceums, colleges, higher educational institutions, it is necessary to activate students' cognitive activity, improve independent and critical thinking abilities [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. After all, it is important for students to know how to sort world information and to learn to distinguish what is important and what is not important [13].

J.Still, K.Meredis, Ch.Temple, D.Dury, I.T.Agapov and many other scientists on critical thinking conducted scientific research and gave their definitions to this concept. In Particular, J.Still, K.Meredis, Ch.Temple's ("reading and writing to promote critical thinking") guide states that teaching as a system of universal foundations, in which the large-scale application of interactive teaching styles allows for effective development of critical thought.

I.T.Agapov said, "Critical thinking - students need to develop the skills of working with text, acquire all forms of oral and written speech, exchange ideas with peers on a specific text (communication skills, group work skills) is a directed pedagogical technology" [14].

Critical thinking changes the atmosphere in the classroom, gives it a sense of excitement, and turns the lessons into a joy for the teacher and the student. Such a technology is based on ideas such as the plurality of points of view of thinking and interpreting the text, reflexivity of the cognitive process, modern understanding of culture. The idea of personal worth and the unquestionable priority of creating favorable conditions for its development, self-realization and realization are considered the most important.

As stated in the project "Reading, writing and critical thinking" (RWCT), the teaching process consists of three stages: invitation, understanding, reflection.

The first stage is called the motivation stage. Using active methods in teaching at the invitation stage, students can receive assignments, create a list of what they already know or think they know through the "Brainstorming" method. In this case, "Brainstorming" is conducted individually or in pairs, and then with the participation of the whole group. A student writes the group brainstorming ideas on the board, regardless of whether they are correct or incorrect. Then the teacher can ask students questions that are directly related to the topic, but not discussed. During this stage, it is important that the teacher speaks as little as possible and allows students to speak more. The main task of a student leader is to act as a guide and to listen carefully to the opinions of students who do not fully master the subjects in the class or group, who are slow in the learning process, and whose thinking skills are not sufficiently developed. Several important types of pedagogical activities are carried out at this stage. First, the learner actively participates

in restoring what he knows about the subject. This forces him to analyze his knowledge and start thinking about a topic that will soon be covered in detail. It should always be remembered that if the information is offered to the student without connecting it to the body of knowledge that is already there, it will soon be forgotten. Because the educational process is the process of acquiring and gathering new knowledge. Students should actively participate in the educational process in order to consciously and thoroughly understand new information. If the student thinks based on the set goal and expresses thoughts in his own words, then his participation will be active. Demonstration of the student's acquired knowledge with the help of oral and written speech, to himself or his partner, takes place in the activity of active thinking. Thus, previously acquired knowledge is brought to the level of awareness. Now, previously acquired knowledge can be the basis for mastering new knowledge. This gives students the opportunity to effectively connect new information with what they already know and prepares the ground for understanding.

The second stage is the awareness stage. At this stage, the student communicates with new information or ideas. This communication can be in the form of reading a text, watching a movie, listening to a speech or conducting experiments. This stage is the stage where the teacher has the least influence on the students during the teaching process. It is at this stage that the student should be independent and actively involved in this work. There are such teaching strategies that always keep the students' activity at a high level, whose activity is slow and their thinking skills are not sufficiently developed. For example, there is the insert method (an interactive system of symbols for effective reading and critical thinking). The insert method is a powerful tool that allows students to actively monitor their own understanding of the learning process. The implementation of the comprehension stage is important in the process of acquiring knowledge, because if the student's ability is weak, he can lose the opportunity to teach him.

The third stage is the thinking stage. In this way, students consolidate new knowledge, add and assimilate new ideas and concepts to the previously existing ones. It is at the thinking stage that several important goals are planned. First of all, students should try to express new ideas and information in their own words. It is essential to generate new ideas and critical thinking. For this, it is necessary to improve the efficiency of the educational process and further improve the quality of education by introducing modern pedagogical technologies of teaching into the educational process. In this regard, President Sh.M. Mirziyoev gave the following instructions: "...in my opinion, it is necessary to solve two main tasks:

- first - the material and technical base of scientific institutions should be significantly strengthened at the level of advanced foreign centers and in accordance with the requirements of scientists. In this, of course, the needs of the state and its target tasks must be taken into account;
- the second - development and implementation of specific measures for all-round support of academics, including financial incentives [12], and the development and implementation of a system of specific measures in this regard implementation tasks were defined.

Thus, the importance of the challenge stage of critical thinking is that it is the student's ability to use new knowledge for an independently chosen purpose. In the second stage of thinking, understanding, new information is connected with the information activated in the stage of invitation. In the third stage of reading, writing, and critical thinking, knowledge is reinforced through reflection.

References

1. Abdinazarovich, R. D. (2023). PATRIOTIC HYMN IN THE NATIONAL SPIRITUAL HERITAGE (AS AN EXAMPLE OF UZBEK FOLK PROVERBS). *Academia Science Repository*, 4(5), 1049-1058.
2. Abdinazarovich, R. D., Sapparbayevna, J. N., & Jo'rayevna, N. N. (2023). OILALARNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARINI SOTSIOLOGIK TAHLILI (HARBIY XIZMATCHILARNING OILASI MISOLIDA). *World of Science*, 6(5), 29-33.
3. Abdinazarovich, R. D. (2023). SOME COMMENTS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY SOCIOLOGY IN UZBEKISTAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 646-650.
4. Abdinazarovich, R. D., Jo'rayevna, N. N., & Sapparbayevna, J. N. (2023). MARKAZIY OSIYO MINTAQASIDA IJTIMOY XIZMATNING SHAKLLANISH GENEZISI. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 6(4), 1005-1009.
5. Abdumannapovna, M. D., & Juraevna, N. N. (2022). THE ROLE OF SOCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG PEOPLE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10 (6), 67–70.
6. Jo'rayevna, N. N. (2023). GIYOHVANDLIK DELINKVENT XULQ SIFATIDA NAMOYON BO 'LISHI. *FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES*, 2(22), 186-189.

7. Jo'rayevna, N. N., & Abdumannapovna, M. D. (2023). MUTAXASSISLIK FANLAR MODULINI O 'QITISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *PEDAGOG*, 6(1), 605-609.
8. Manapovna, G. Z., Abdumannapovna, M. D., & Jo'rayevna, N. N. (2023). TRANSPORT SOHASIDA KADRLAR KASBIY KOMPETENSIYASINING AHAMIYATI. *PEDAGOG*, 6(1), 615-618.
9. Nosirov, R., Yunusova, N., Nazarova, N., & Shamsiddinova, E. (2023, June). Occupational problems in youth competitiveness. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2789, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
10. Saparbayevna, J. N., Jo'rayevna, N. N., & Abdinazarovich, R. D. (2023). YOSHLARDA MAS'ULIYAT HISSINI TARBIYALASHNING IJTIMOY-FALSAFIY MOHIYATI. *World of Science*, 6(5), 25-28.
11. Saparbayevna, J. N., Jo'rayevna, N. N., & Niyazmatovich, R. Z. (2023). YOSHLAR INTELLEKTUAL BILIMINI OSHIRISHDA PRAGMATIK FIKRLASHNING AHAMIYATI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(10), 136-140.
12. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Танқидий таҳлил, қатъий тартиб-интизом ва шахсий жавобгарлик - ҳар бир раҳбар фаолиятининг кундалик қондаси бўлиши керак. - Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2017. 46 – бет.
13. Назарова, Н. (2023). STRUCTURAL-FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF ENSURING PROFESSIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF YOUTH OF UZBEKISTAN. *ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ*, 6(2).
14. Сайидахмедов Н.С, Абдурахимов С. Педагогик технология ва педагогик маҳорат. Иқтисод молия–Т.: 2010. -Б.104.